

Synthesis of a new water reducing agent

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Abstract : The preparation of water reducing agents from phenanthrene waste has been studied by sulfonation, condensation, neutralization and recondensation. Reaction conditions were investigated by orthogonal test, and main technical parameters optimized. The optimum conditions were as follows : molar ratio of phenanthrene to sulfuric acid (1 : 2), sulfonation temperature (160 °C), sulfonation time (3 h), molar ratio of phenanthrene to formaldehyde (1 : 1), condensation temperature (80 °C), condensation time (3 h), molar ratio of phenanthrene to carbamide (1 : 0.005), recondensation temperature (80 °C). The study showed that the water reducing agent synthesized in the work was high effective.

Keywords : Water reducing agents, phenanthrene.

The study described the synthesis of water reducing agents from phenanthrene waste by sulfonation, condensation, neutralization and recondensation. Phenanthrene waste, which contained mainly phenanthrene (about 50%), and a small quantity of anthracene, carbazole, etc. was a residue/by-product after isolation of anthracene and carbazole from crude anthracene. Since an effective industrial use for the residue has not been found in China, it was commonly heaped in manufacturer as the form of a waste, seriously polluting the environment. Thereby, the preparation of water reducing agents from phenanthrene waste

could reach the purposes of developing a high effective water reducing agent, cleansing the environment and offering an effective way of industrial use.

Experimental

Materials : Phenanthrene waste was obtained from a local market. For sulfonation, condensation, neutralization and recondensation, commercial grade chemicals were used.

The water reducing agent was synthesized by reactions as follows :

(1) Sulfonation :

(2) Condensation :

(3) Neutralization :

(4) Recondensation :

The recondensation based on Mannich' reaction :

The agents were prepared from phenanthrene waste in proportion as phenanthrene : sulfuric acid : formaldehyde : carbamide = 1 : 1.5 ~ 2.5 : 0.8 ~ 1.2 : 0.005 ~ 0.01 (molar ratio). Procedures as follows : To a stirred reactor filled with phenanthrene waste, concentrated sulfuric acid was proportionally added drop by drop at 130 °C. Then the temperature was kept at 120 °C ~ 160 °C, and phenanthrene waste was sulfonated for 2 ~ 4 h. The temperature was lowered to 60 ~ 80 °C. The formaldehyde (aqueous solution, 40% by weight) was dropwise added to the reactor in 60 min, then the sulfonate was condensed with formaldehyde at 70 ~ 90 °C for 2 ~ 4 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with caustic soda at 60 ~ 80 °C until pH of 7 ~ 9 was achieved. Finally, aqueous products were obtained by recondensation with carbamide at 80 ~ 90 °C for 60 min.

Agents characterization : The application properties of the agent developed in this study were investigated by a water reducing test according to Chinese Standard GB8076-1997 (Concret Admixtures), and quantitatively expressed with water reducing rates (water-reduction percentage) :

$$\text{Water reducing rate (\%)} = (W_0 - W_1)/W_0 \times 100$$

where, W_0 = unit water dosage of concrete without agents at a given workability (kg/m^3),

W_1 = unit water dosage of concrete with agents at the same workability as above (kg/m^3).

The measurements were carried out by using the local cement, and the addition (solid content) of agents was 0.3% of cement of weight.

Results and discussion

Taking the water reducing rates as the object function, and the conditions such as molar ratio of reagents, reaction time and temperature as variable factors, we evaluated the effects of eight factors on the function and optimized the eight technological parameters by using the table of $L_{18}(2 \times 3^7)^1$ (i.e. an orthogonal table of 18 rows (18 times of test), 8 columns (8 factors : A = recondensation temperature, B = molar ratio of phenanthrene to carbamide, C = sulfonation temperature, D = sulfonation time, E = molar ratio of phenanthrene to sulfuric acid, F = condensation temperature, G = condensation time, H = molar ratio of phenanthrene to formaldehyde), and 2 levels and 3 levels : 80 °C, 90 °C; 1 : 0.005, 1 : 0.008, 1 : 0.01; 120 °C, 140 °C, 160 °C; 2 h, 3 h, 4 h; 1 : 1.5, 1 : 2, 1 : 2.5; 70 °C, 80 °C, 90 °C; 2 h,

3 h, 4 h; 1 : 1.0, 1 : 1.1, 1 : 1.2). The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2. With range analysis and variance analysis of effects of each factor on the function, we found that, among these factors, the order of influence upon water reducing percentages was as follows : molar ratio of phenanthrene to sulfuric acid > molar ratio of phenanthrene to carbamide > condensation temperature > recondensation temperature > molar ratio of phenanthrene to formaldehyde > condensation time > sulfonation temperature > sulfonation time, the optimum conditions : molar ratio of phenanthrene to sulfuric acid : 1 : 2, sulfonation temperature : 160 °C, time 3 h, molar ratio of phenanthrene to formaldehyde : 1 : 1, condensation temperature : 80 °C, time 3 h, molar ratio of phenanthrene to carbamide : 1 : 0.005, recondensation temperature : 80 °C and because $F_A < F_{0.25}(1,2) = 2.57$ and the rest : $F < F_{0.25}(2,2) = 3.0$, there were no notable factors for influencing water reducing rates.

The water-reduction percentages of the water reducing agent prepared through repeated experiments under the optimum conditions were as follows : 16.5, 16.8, 17.0, 17.5, 16.9 which was greater than 15%. It was shown that the agent was a high effective one and had the same effect of water reducing as a standard water reducing agent from naphthalene² (its water reducing rate was also greater than 15%).

In order to study the efficacy of this water-reducing agent, the water reducing rates were determined at various dosages (0.3 ~ 0.8% of cement by weight) of the water-reducing agent. The results are shown in Table 3. Table 3 indicates that the water-reducing percentage increases with the dosage. The experiments show that the product prepared under the optimum conditions has a higher water-reduction percentage and a little additive.

Conclusion :

- (i) By orthogonal test main technical parameters were optimized. The optimum conditions were as follows : molar ratio of phenanthrene to sulfuric acid : 1 : 2; sulfonation temperature : 160 °C; sulfonation time : 3 h; molar ratio of phenanthrene to formaldehyde : 1 : 1; condensation temperature : 80 °C; condensation time : 3 h; molar ratio of phenanthrene to carbamide : 1 : 0.005; recondensation temperature : 80 °C.
- (ii) The study showed that the product synthesized under the optimum conditions had a higher water reducing rate and a little additive.

Table 1. Orthogonal test and range analysis

No.	Factors								Water reducing rates
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.118
2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.159
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.153
4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.110
5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.114
6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.087
7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.107
8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.115
9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.122
10	-	-	-	L ₁₈ (2 × 3 ⁷)		-	-	-	0.132
11	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.070
12	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.117
13	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.095
14	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.090
15	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.124
16	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.114
17	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.114
18	-	-	-			-	-	-	0.117
K ₁	1.085	0.749	0.676	0.658	0.589	0.646	0.675	0.720	
K ₂	0.973	0.620	0.662	0.709	0.739	0.730	0.723	0.647	
K ₃		0.689	0.720	0.691	0.730	0.682	0.660	0.691	
k ₁	0.121	0.125	0.113	0.110	0.098	0.108	0.113	0.120	
k ₂	0.108	0.103	0.110	0.118	0.123	0.122	0.121	0.108	
k ₃		0.115	0.120	0.115	0.122	0.114	0.110	0.115	
R	1.3	2.2	1.0	0.8	2.5	1.4	1.1	1.2	

*K₁, Sum of water reducing rates of the level i; k₁, average of K_i; R (range), R = k_{max} - k_{min}.

Table 2. Variance analysis

Factors	Square sum	Liberal degree	Mean square	F	Notability
A	6.969	1	6.969	1.027	
B	13.890	2	6.945	1.023	
C	3.053	2	1.527	0.225	
D	2.230	2	1.115	0.164	
E	23.590	2	11.795	1.738	
F	5.920	2	2.960	0.436	
G	3.610	2	1.805	0.266	
H	4.503	2	2.252	0.332	
Error	13.575	2	6.788		
Sum	77.340	17			

F_A < F_{0.25} (1,2) = 2.57; the rest of the factors : F < F_{0.25} (2,2) = 3.0.

* Mean square = square sum/liberal degree.

F = mean square of factors/mean square of error.

Table 3. The effect of dosage on the water-reduction percentage

Dosage (%)	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8
Water reducing rate (%)	17.5	18.4	19.0	19.9	22.4	24.0

(iii) Since it was a residue/by-product after anthracene recovery from crude anthracene, this by product, which was commonly piled in manufacturer as a waste, could be available in a plentiful supply, so that the development of a commercial might be undertaken, and the cost of the water reducing agent was lower than commercial agents, which were costly materials, e.g. naphthalene, melamine, etc.

(iv) The water-reducing agent obtained from phenanthrene waste had these advantages of developing a high effective agent, cleansing the environment and offering an effective way of industrial use.

Note

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